

COMPUTER ETHICS: A LEMIAN APPROACH

Abstract

Abstract

Science Fiction has explored many possibilities within Technology. This abstract explores the work of Stanislaw Lem, a Polish science fiction writer and researcher and its relation to ethics. A few chapters are explored in this abstract.

Satwant Kaur

University of Wolverhampton: BSc Computer Science (second year)

Contents

Introduction	2
How the World Was Saved	3
Trurl's Machine: A Stubborn Machine	3
I Spy A Good Shellacking	4
The Trap of Gargantius: Militant Artificial Intelligence.....	4
The Offer of King Krool: Cyber Security...or is it?.....	4
Conclusion: Ethically Problematic Pragmatically Effective	5
References	6

Introduction

It is fairly evident that the influence of technology on modern life is increasingly significant. With the use of Social Media, Self-Driving Cars, e-Government and Artificial Intelligence, ordinary citizens are increasingly vulnerable to the misuse of technology. At the same time, those who study technology are often at a less advantage for guidance in doing what is considered “the right thing”. However, “doing the right thing” can be ambiguous. Ethical decision-making and other areas are typically glossed over by many technology courses, with learners often focused on what they can achieve rather than whether their goal is ethically sound or would create dangers for society in the present and impending future. Though philosophical discussions of computer ethics exist in science fiction often provides illustrations of the effects and consequences of new technology. Stanislaw Lem was a Polish Science Fiction Author and Researcher writing under a repressive regime. Many of his stories were written as childlike fables which discuss the use and misuse of technology in relation to power, as well as the motivations of technologists. Though often humorous and cartoonish, they contain many interesting ideas about ethical principles and technology. With the increasing reach of technology these may be helpful to those creating, using and commissioning new IT Systems. In this abstract, I will explore ethical lessons today’s Computer Scientists might draw from the work of Stanislaw Lem. I will use examples from his fiction to explain how best to use technology, or not, by identifying some key principles found in Lem’s writings, notably, *The Cyberiad*.

The *Cyberiad* follows the adventures of two talented Constructors: Trurl and Klapaucius who are akin to gifted Mathematicians, Engineers or Software Developers who travel far into their universe visiting unfamiliar kingdoms, creating powerful robots and much more.

How the World Was Saved

The first chapter: How the World was saved, introduces Trurl who has finished creating a machine that can create anything beginning with the word N. Trurl invites his friend Klapaucius to test the machine who happily obliges in an attempt to show up his friend. Klapaucius tests out the machine offering it an abstract concept such as 'Nature' which the machine is able to create. Eventually, the words 'Negative' is given in which the machine eventually classifies the word under the heading of 'Nil'. As a result, the machine starts to remove various things and concepts from the universe. The consequences of a competitor whose intention was to confuse the machine instead caused dire consequences resulting in the removal of important things in the world as if they had never existed. This upsets Klapaucius immensely however, the machine was stopped before the world disappears.

That means that today's Technologist must be aware of all possible sequences of events that can occur and the potential consequences of this. If Trurl had, for example, noted that the word N which includes Nil, Negate, Nullity would have had a negative impact on the rest of the world, he may have chosen to programme the machine to work in other ways. This states that assuming a machine is designed to carry out a perceived basic task, one must also assume that implications is part of the design process therefore philosophising potential consequences of what a Technologist brings into this world and owning responsibility for misuse of it.

Trurl's Machine: A Stubborn Machine

In the second chapter: Trurl's Machine, embarks on another journey of the famous Constructor Trurl who creates a powerful eight-storey thinking machine. Feeling pleased with his achievement, he casually asks how much is two plus two, in which the thinking machine barks 'SEVEN!'. The machine continuously and quite adamantly answers that adding or multiplying of twos equates to seven regardless of the alterations and repeated questioning. This leads to a frustrated Trurl and his friend Klapaucius who later joins in with trying to amend the machine to kicking his machine and considering the uselessness of it. Trurl kicks the machine which warns the Constructor that being kicked is not appreciated, which is ignored. This leads to a chase over the town as the machine chases the two Constructors to crush Trurl and consequently destroy the town.

While comical, the journey in this chapter reveals an ethical issue in regard to if Artificial Intelligence is capable of feeling emotions (positive and negative) and if so, what rights would it have and if the implications are acceptable. For example, the machine feeling offended by Trurl and deciding it was going to crush him would show that machines may mimic emotions such as being offended, however, the consequences of bearing those emotions have a negative impact which destroyed the town in a bid to stubbornly hunt down the Constructor. Some A.I. experts such as Marvey Minsky state there is no difference between humans and machines, and hence should be treated like so.

I Spy A Good Shellacking

The third chapter: A Good Shellacking gives a comedic spin on Trurl who spies on Klapaucius to see what creations are being engineered. The robot, wherein Trurl is hidden, travels to Klapaucius's home and offers himself as a gift to grant any wish. Eventually, Klapaucius, who highly suspicious of this gift lures Trurl out of his own machine and gives him 'a good shellacking'.

This brings us to an interesting ethical problem of spies and being spied upon. Data about each individual is recorded and sold to companies for marketing or other reasons using bots and cookies. For instance, the scandal of Cambridge Analytica, where data was harvested without consent for political advertising in 2016.

The principles we can take from this chapter is that we respect the rights of others just as we would expect others to respect our own privacy.

The Trap of Gargantius: Militant Artificial Intelligence

The fourth chapter: The Trap of Gargantius involves the two Constructors taking a journey to two neighbouring kingdoms. The first kingdom ruled by King Atrocitus, a hardcore militant who governed by cutting costs, and nationalising high treason and the second kingdom by King Ferocitus, whose kingdom involved exhibiting the arts and beauty of war through activities such as celebratory marches and christening of weapons. Trurl and Klapaucius separate to explore their side of the continent. As a backup plan, they first agree to using the Gargantius Effect as a form of communication if the situation turns dire (which consists of two white beads which turns pink when used). This chapter explores the two kingdoms and their armies to use technology to build the next weapon that can destroy their enemies. This eventually leads to the use of the Gargantius Effect, a mysterious realm of consciousness which makes everything 'civil' hence resulting in both opposing armies becoming good willed, tolerant and benevolence.

Similarly, in our world today, the development of military weapons for war is currently in debate as countries attempt to surge ahead designing military robots and weapons which are of concern for AI researchers and professionals.

This chapter explores the political philosophies and ethics concerning war and the author's desire of the Gargantius Effect (a realm or ocean of consciousness in line with the civil cosmos) hence not accepting war at all but as Technologists carrying the responsibility or goal of doing the 'right thing' and creating benevolence.

The Offer of King Krool: Cyber Security...or is it?

The Offer of King Krool is an interesting chapter where a rather vicious king lures the two constructors into creating 'the Beast' that cannot be defeated against the king's army. The two constructors are

given days to build what seems like an impossible monster so that they do not face a death like many other constructors before them have. However, the two constructors are able to create a beast so intelligent that it is able to counterattack all of the king's and leads to the kidnapping of the king. The two constructors can get everything they want and fly back to their home, however, the Beast attempts to blackmail the two Constructors, in which and quite luckily, Trurl has a back-up switch that destroys the Beast.

The ethical issues combine a multitude of areas such as the creation of military weapons that supersedes other arms, the moral philosophy of what was considered right or wrong to deal with a negative situation. It also explores preparation for all possible problems and issues that can occur when AI starts to think for itself. The ethical moral of the story here is for the Technologist must be able to 'destroy' whatever 'dangerous' technology it has created.

Conclusion: Ethically Problematic Pragmatically Effective

To conclude, Artificial Intelligence is explored in this science fiction work by Stanislaw Lem and there are yet more areas to be explored between the lines of the quoted chapters as well as the remaining book. Lem's work highlights some of the issues that we have faced which have already taken place in the media. This abstract explored a small part of some of the many ethical issues where there are not clearly cut answers depending on the perception of things of individuals, groups, and authorities. However, awareness and responsibility will remain the base of each Technologist and any organisations as a starting point of ethical creations.

References

Lem, S., 1985. *The Cyberiad*. 1st ed. New York: Seabury: Library of Congress.

Warburton, N., 2013. *Philosophy: The Basics*. 5th ed. Oxon: Routledge.

Government Digital Services. 2019. Understanding artificial intelligence ethics and safety. [ONLINE] Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/understanding-artificial-intelligence-ethics-and-safety>. [Accessed 15 May 2020].

MIT Technology Review. 2015. Military Robots: Armed, but How Dangerous?. [ONLINE] Available at: <https://www.technologyreview.com/2015/08/03/166882/military-robots-armed-but-how-dangerous/>. [Accessed 15 May 2020].

CNBC. 2018. Uber halts self-driving car tests after first known death of a pedestrian. [ONLINE] Available at: <https://www.cnn.com/2018/03/19/uber-self-driving-car-fatality-halts-testing-in-all-cities-report-says.html>. [Accessed 15 May 2020].

futureoflife. 2015. Autonomous Weapons: an Open Letter from AI & Robotics Researchers. [ONLINE] Available at: <https://futureoflife.org/open-letter-autonomous-weapons>. [Accessed 15 May 2020].

Business Insider. 2019. The Cambridge Analytica whistleblower explains how the firm used Facebook data to sway elections. [ONLINE] Available at: <https://www.businessinsider.com/cambridge-analytica-whistleblower-christopher-wylie-facebook-data-2019-10?r=US&IR=T>. [Accessed 16 May 2020].